

Analysis Plan

Version 1

Causality in the Allostatic Self-Efficacy Theory Using the Perception of
Breathing in the Human Brain Data Set

Alex Hess

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1 Introduction

This document specifies the analysis plan for data from the perception of breathing in the human brain (PBIHB) study conducted at the Translational Neuromodeling Unit (TNU) Zurich and University Hospital Magnetic Resonance Centre. A detailed description of the PBIHB data set can be found elsewhere [6] and the data are freely available for download from the ETH Research Collection (<https://doi.org/10.3929/ethz-b-000503396>).

This analysis plan concerns a set of analyses that are motivated by the allostatic self-efficacy theory (ASE; [14, 8]). Specifically, the scientific questions below concern hypothetical causal relationships between metacognition of allostatic control (M; specifically, the feeling of being in control over one’s own bodily states), fatigue (F), general self-efficacy (S), and depression (D) implied by the ASE theory and by recent experimental findings [13]. In brief, the ASE theory postulates that the subjective experience of fatigue arises when, in a situation of persistent dyshomeostasis, the brain arrives at the metacognitive diagnosis that its control over bodily states is failing; a condition also referred to as low allostatic self-efficacy. Once a generalisation of low self-efficacy beliefs, i.e. the perceived lack of control over bodily states, has taken place and general self-efficacy beliefs are low, this is postulated to trigger the onset of depression [14, 13]. Figure 1 displays a graphical summary of the causal structure implied by the ASE theory in the form of a directed acyclic graph (DAG) G_0 including also the variables age (A) and gender (G), which are known to be related to the central quantities of the ASE theory. However, note that age (A) and gender (G) are not explicitly part of the ASE theory. Hence, the DAG G_0 in figure 1 is representative for the induced observational distribution and the interventional distribution induced by interventions on metacognition of allostatic control (M), fatigue (F) or general self-efficacy (S).

The Structural causal model (SCM; [2, 9, 10]) implied by the ASE theory combined with a linearity assumption is of the following form:

$$A = N_A \tag{1}$$

$$G = N_G \tag{2}$$

$$M = \theta_1 A + \theta_2 G + N_M \tag{3}$$

$$F = \theta_3 M + \theta_4 A + \theta_5 G + N_F \tag{4}$$

$$S = \theta_6 A + \theta_7 G + N_S \tag{5}$$

$$D = \theta_8 F + \theta_9 S + \theta_{10} FS + \theta_{11} A + \theta_{12} G + N_D \tag{6}$$

where A stands for age, G for gender, M for metacognition of allostatic control, F for fatigue, S general self-efficacy, D for depression, and N_i are jointly independent noise variables. $\forall i \neq G$, N_i follows a normal distribution and N_G is a Bernoulli random variable.

As part of the PBIHB data set, the following measurements are available that can be used as representations of the central quantities in the ASE theory:

Figure 1: Directed acyclic graph (DAG) G_0 summarizing the key proposal of the allostatic self-efficacy theory (ASE; [14]). The DAG G_0 is representative for the induced observational distribution and the interventional distribution induced by interventions on metacognition of allostatic control (M), fatigue (F) or general self-efficacy (S).

- **fatigue (F)**: Fatigue Severity Scale (FSS)
- **general self-efficacy (S)**: General Self-Efficacy Scale (GSES)
- **depression (D)**: Centre for Epidemiologic Studies Depression Scale (CES-D)
- **metacognition of allostatic control (M)** (best available approximation of construct of interest):
 - questionnaire-based: subscales 3 and 8 of the Multidimensional Assessment of Interoceptive Awareness (MAIA_{3,8})
 - task-based: metacognitive bias (confidence level, i.e. mean trial-by-trial confidence) and metacognitive efficiency (Mratio) [5]

2 Scientific Questions

1. Do the data of the PBIHB study contradict the causal structure implied by the ASE theory (figure 1)?
2. Assuming the SCM implied by the ASE theory (eqs. 1-6), the average causal effect from metacognition of allostatic control (M) to fatigue (F) is given by $\frac{\partial}{\partial m} \mathbb{E}_{do(M:=m)} [F] = \theta_3$. What is the value of θ_3 ?
3. Assuming the SCM implied by the ASE theory (eqs. 1-6), the average causal effect of the linear interaction term between general self-efficacy (S) and fatigue (F) on depression (D) is given by $\frac{\partial}{\partial f \partial s} \mathbb{E}_{do(F:=f, S:=s)} [D] = \theta_{10}$. What is the value of θ_{10} ?

2.1 Question 1: Causal structure of ASE theory in the PBIHB data set

We assume that the observational distribution \mathbb{P} induced by the SCM (eqs. 1-6) is Markov and faithful w.r.t. the DAG G_0 . In other words, we assume a one-to-one correspondence between graphical separation properties between the corresponding nodes and conditional independences in the distribution [15].

Hypothesis 1: Data from the PBIHB study satisfy the following conditional independence statements:

- (i) $M \perp\!\!\!\perp S \mid A, G$
- (ii) $M \perp\!\!\!\perp D \mid F, A, G$ and $M \perp\!\!\!\perp D \mid F, A, G, S$
- (iii) $F \perp\!\!\!\perp S \mid A, G$ and $F \perp\!\!\!\perp S \mid A, G, M$

The statistical analysis will be conducted as follows:

- statistical test:
 - asymptotic χ^2 test (mutual information) for mixed discrete and normal variables
 - exact Student’s t test for Pearson’s linear correlation between normal variables
- variables of interest: MAIA_{3,8}, FSS, GSES, CES-D, age, gender
- statistical threshold: p -value $\leq \frac{0.05}{5} = 0.01$
- sensitivity analysis:
 - rerun for task-based measures of metacognition of allostatic control (M; metacognitive bias, metacognitive efficiency) separately

2.2 Question 2: Estimating the average causal effect from metacognition of allostatic control to fatigue

Hypothesis 2: There is a negative average causal effect from metacognition of allostatic control (M) to fatigue (F).

To test this hypothesis, we will use different methods for estimating causal effects, including covariate adjustment [11], the ”propensity score” method [12] and double/debiased machine learning (DML; [3]). This allows us to assess the robustness of the estimated effect by comparing the results obtained from the different methods.

2.2.1 Covariate Adjustment

Assuming the SCM implied by the ASE theory (eq. 1-6), we can estimate the average causal effect from metacognition of allostatic control (M) to fatigue (F)

using linear regression, since

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial m} \mathbb{E}_{do(M:=m)} [F] = \frac{\partial}{\partial m} (\theta_3 m + E[\theta_4 A + \theta_5 G + N_F]) = \theta_3$$

Details of the analysis are as follows:

- statistical model: linear regression
- dependent variable: fatigue (FSS)
- independent variables: metacognition of allostatic control (MAIA_{3,8})
- covariates (valid adjustment set; VAS): age, gender
- statistical test: one-sided t -test
- statistical threshold: p -value $\leq \frac{0.05}{3} \approx 0.017$
- sensitivity analyses:
 - rerun using a different VAS: age, gender, GSES
 - rerun for task-based measures for metacognition of allostatic control (M; metacognitive bias, metacognitive efficiency) separately

2.2.2 Propensity Score

In the statistical analysis of observational data, the "propensity score" method is a technique that attempts to estimate the causal effect of an exposure M on outcome F by accounting for a set of confounders $\mathbf{Z} = (A, G)$ that predict the probability of the exposure [4]. The idea is to adjust for \mathbf{Z} when estimating the effect of exposure M by weighting observations i by inverse probability weights.

Details of the propensity score analysis are as follows:

- statistical model: generalised linear model with inverse-probability weighting (IPW) and design-based standard errors as implemented in the **survey** package [7]
- dependent variable: fatigue (FSS)
- independent variables: metacognition of allostatic control (MAIA_{3,8})
- covariates (VAS): $\mathbf{Z} = (A, G)$
- standardised weights of M for IPW:

$$sw_i = \frac{f(m_i)}{f(m_i | \mathbf{z}_i)}$$

estimate using linear regression under normality assumptions for both the numerator and the denominator

- statistical test: one-sided t -test

- statistical threshold: $p\text{-value} \leq \frac{0.05}{3} \approx 0.017$
- sensitivity analyses:
 - rerun using a different VAS: age, gender, GSES
 - rerun for task-based measures for metacognition of allostatic control (M; metacognitive bias, metacognitive efficiency) separately

2.2.3 Double Machine Learning

DML removes the impact of regularisation bias and overfitting on estimation of the parameter of interest θ_3 by using Neyman-orthogonal moments and cross-fitting [3]. We will use DML to estimate θ_3 in the following partial linear regression model

$$F = M\theta_3 + g_0(\mathbf{Z}) + N_F, \quad \mathbb{E}(N_F | M, \mathbf{Z}) = 0, \quad (7)$$

$$M = m_0(\mathbf{Z}) + V, \quad \mathbb{E}(V | \mathbf{Z}) = 0, \quad (8)$$

with fatigue F , metacognition of allostatic control M , a VAS $\mathbf{Z} = (A, G)$ consisting of confounding covariates and stochastic error terms N_F and V . The confounding covariates \mathbf{Z} affect M and F via the functions m_0 and g_0 , respectively. θ_3 is the main regression coefficient that we would like to infer, which can be interpreted as the average causal effect from M to F [1].

Details of the DML analysis are as follows:

- statistical model: partially linear regression model
- dependent variable: fatigue (FSS)
- independent variables: metacognition of allostatic control (MAIA_{3,8})
- covariates (VAS): age, gender
- sample splitting: split data set into 2 random partitions by dividing it into equal parts and use cross-fitting on the different splits
- ML method to estimate nuisance parameters: random regression forest
- score ψ defined for the average causal effect: IV-type, i.e.

$$\psi(W; \theta_3, \eta) := (F - M\theta_3 - g(\mathbf{Z}))(M - m(\mathbf{Z})),$$

$$\eta = (g, m), \quad \eta_0 = (g_0, m_0)$$

with g and m being P -square-integrable functions mapping the support of \mathbf{Z} to \mathbb{R} with values given by

$$g_0 = \mathbb{E}[F - M\theta_3 | \mathbf{Z}], \quad m_0(\mathbf{Z}) = \mathbb{E}[M | \mathbf{Z}]$$

- statistical test: one-sided t -test

- statistical threshold: $p\text{-value} \leq \frac{0.05}{3} \approx 0.017$
- sensitivity analyses:
 - rerun using a different VAS: age, gender, GSES
 - rerun for task-based measures for metacognition of allostatic control (M; metacognitive bias, metacognitive efficiency) separately

2.3 Question 3: Estimating the average causal effect of the interaction term between fatigue and general self-efficacy on depression

Hypothesis 3: There is a negative average causal effect of the interaction term between fatigue (F) and general self-efficacy (S) on depression (D).

Following the reasoning above, we will use the same set of methods for estimating causal effects as we did for the evaluation of scientific question 2.

2.3.1 Covariate Adjustment

Assuming the SCM implied by the ASE theory (eq. 1-6), we can estimate the average causal effect from F*S to D using linear regression, since

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\partial}{\partial f \partial s} \mathbb{E}_{do(F:=f, S:=s)} [D] \\ &= \frac{\partial}{\partial f \partial s} (\theta_8 f + \theta_9 s + \theta_{10} f s + E[\theta_{11} A + \theta_{12} G + N_D]) \\ &= \theta_{10} \end{aligned}$$

Details of the analysis are as follows:

- statistical model: linear regression
- dependent variable: depression (CES-D)
- independent variables: fatigue (FSS), general self-efficacy (GSES), linear interaction term between fatigue and general self-efficacy (FSS*GSES)
- covariates (VAS): age, gender
- statistical test: one-sided t -test
- statistical threshold: $p\text{-value} \leq \frac{0.05}{3} \approx 0.017$
- sensitivity analyses:
 - rerun using a different VAS: age, gender, MAIA_{3,8}
 - rerun for task-based measures for metacognition of allostatic control (M; metacognitive bias, metacognitive efficiency) separately

2.3.2 Propensity Score

Details of the propensity score analysis are as follows:

- statistical model: generalised linear model with inverse-probability weighting (IPW) and design-based standard errors as implemented in the **survey** package [7]
- dependent variable: depression (CES-D)
- independent variables: fatigue (FSS), general self-efficacy (GSES), linear interaction term between fatigue and general self-efficacy (FSS*GSES)
- covariates (VAS): $\mathbf{Z} = (A, G)$
- standardised weights of F*S for IPW:

$$sw_i = \frac{f(f_i, s_i)}{f(f_i, s_i | \mathbf{z}_i)}$$

estimate using linear regression under normality assumptions for both the numerator and the denominator

- statistical test: one-sided t -test
- statistical threshold: p -value $\leq \frac{0.05}{3} \approx 0.017$
- sensitivity analyses:
 - rerun using a different VAS: age, gender, MAIA_{3,8}
 - rerun for task-based measures for metacognition of allostatic control (M; metacognitive bias, metacognitive efficiency) separately

2.3.3 Double Machine Learning

Details of the DML analysis are as follows:

- statistical model: partially linear regression model
- dependent variable: depression (CES-D)
- independent variables: fatigue (FSS), general self-efficacy (GSES), linear interaction term between fatigue and general self-efficacy (FSS*GSES)
- covariates (VAS): age, gender
- sample splitting: split data set into 2 random partitions by dividing it into equal parts and use cross-fitting on the different splits
- ML method to estimate nuisance parameters: random regression forest
- score ψ defined for the average causal effect: IV-type, i.e.

$$\psi(W; \theta_3, \eta) := (F - D\theta_3 - g(\mathbf{Z}))(D - m(\mathbf{Z})),$$

$$\eta = (g, m), \quad \eta_0 = (g_0, m_0)$$

with g and m being P -square-integrable functions mapping the support of \mathbf{Z} to \mathbb{R} with values given by

$$g_0 = \mathbb{E}[F - D\theta_3 | \mathbf{Z}], \quad m_0(\mathbf{Z}) = \mathbb{E}[D | \mathbf{Z}]$$

and $D = F * S$

- statistical test: one-sided t -test
- statistical threshold: p -value $\leq \frac{0.05}{3} \approx 0.017$
- sensitivity analyses:
 - rerun using a different VAS: age, gender, MAIA_{3,8}
 - rerun for task-based measures for metacognition of allostatic control (M; metacognitive bias, metacognitive efficiency) separately

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